

Research Article

Beyond Monolingualism: Ensemble Methods for Bengali Dialect Classification

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ABSTRACT

Dialects are linguistic variations that emerge based on geographical and cultural differences. Bengali, as one of the most widely spoken languages, exhibits significant dialectal diversity across different regions. This research focuses on classifying six major Bengali dialects: Chatgaiya, Barishali, Sylheti, Noakhaila, Mymensingh, and Rangpuri. We introduce the *Bengali Local Dialects Corpus*, a dataset consisting of 8,149 spoken phrases collected from native speakers and digital sources such as social media and online content. To process the dataset, we applied extensive text preprocessing and explored multiple feature extraction techniques, including Bag of Words, Word2Vec, and TF-IDF with n-gram features. Various machine learning and deep learning models were evaluated to identify the most effective approach for dialect classification. Among all methods, an ensemble Voting Classifier demonstrated the highest accuracy of 88.74%, outperforming both traditional and deep learning models. These results highlight the potential of ensemble learning in dialect classification, offering a robust approach for analyzing regional linguistic variations in Bengali. The findings of this research can contribute to speech recognition, language translation, and linguistic studies focused on low-resource languages.

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Introduction

Dialect refers to the variation of a language based on geography, culture, and social factors. Bengali, one of the most spoken languages worldwide, exhibits significant dialectal differences across various regions of Bangladesh. While dialect classification is an essential area in Natural Language Processing (NLP) (Jurafsky & Martin, 2021), much of the existing research has focused on speech-based dialect recognition rather than text-based dialect classification. However, the rise of social media and digital communication platforms has increased the need to process and analyze Bengali dialectal texts. Traditional text classification methods have been used for tasks like fake news detection, sentiment analysis (Hassan et al., 2020), and cyberbullying detection (Manning & Schütze, 1999). However, the complexity of Bengali dialects, including phonetic, lexical, and syntactic variations, presents unique challenges. Previous work in this area (Bhattacharjee & Das, 2022) focused on dialect classification with only two dialect classes, which we found to be somewhat vague, considering the richness of Bengali dialects. Since there are many more distinct dialects, we extended this research by classifying the dialects into six major classes. This study addresses these challenges by leveraging an ensemble learning-based classification approach. We collected and developed a dataset comprising six major Bengali dialects and applied machine learning and deep learning models to classify them. Our experimental results show that the ensemble Voting Classifier outperforms all other models, achieving the highest accuracy in dialect classification.

Language barriers in communication arise when people from different regions travel, making it difficult to understand the local dialect. Teachers and students from different regions face conversational gaps due to linguistic variations. Dialect classification supports inclusive educational technologies by enabling automated tutoring and assessment systems to accurately understand student inputs expressed in regional Bengali dialects. Efficient dialect classification can also aid applications such as telemedicine, online services, and regional sentiment analysis.

This work involves the development of a novel dataset, the Bengali Local Dialects Corpus, consisting of 8,149 sentences representing six major dialects of Bangladesh. It implements advanced feature extraction techniques, including TF-IDF with n-gram features and Bag of Words with skip-gram training. Multiple classification models are evaluated, among which the ensemble Voting Classifier achieves the best performance. Additionally, the study explores deep learning-based approaches for dialect classification, which have not been extensively used for Bengali textual dialect classification.

The dialect classification problem is formulated as a multi-class text classification task. Given a set of input sentences $S = \{S_1, S_2, \dots, S_n\}$, each belonging to one of six dialect classes $C = \{C_1, C_2, \dots, C_6\}$, our goal is to learn a mapping function:

$$f : S \rightarrow C, \quad f(s_i) = \arg \max_{c_j \in C} P(c_j | \text{features}(s_i)) \quad (1)$$

where $P(C_j | \text{features}(S_i))$ represents the probability of sentence S_i belonging to class C_j , based on extracted linguistic features. The model is trained to maximize this probability for accurate classification.

Literature Review

Several studies have explored dialect classification, sentiment analysis, misinformation detection, and fake news identification using machine learning and deep learning techniques. Hassan et al. (2025) introduced RegSpeech12, a large speech corpus spanning multiple dialect regions, facilitating phonetic and morphological analysis for dialect technologies. Similarly, Kabir and Chowdhury (2025) developed the BengDiDa dataset with extensive audio dialect samples, enabling deeper exploration of identification models. Advances in machine translation for dialectal varieties have been explored using retrieval-augmented generation (Sami et al., 2025), demonstrating improved translation performance from Standard Bengali to regional variants. Khandaker et al. (2025) compared multiple neural models for dialect translation, showing neural NMT systems can effectively capture dialectal nuance. The BanglaDial text dataset (Mahi et al., 2025) offers a merged large-scale text corpus across eleven Bengali dialects, addressing an under-resourced area in dialectal NLP and providing representative samples for classification tasks. Tomal et al. (2022) classified Bangla dialects using ML models, achieving 96% accuracy with LR and MNB. Lulu and Elnagar (2018) classified Arabic dialects using CNN, LSTM, and BLSTM, where BLSTM achieved 83.8% accuracy in binary classification. Nayel et al. (2021) worked on Arabic dialect detection from tweets, where CNB outperformed others in dialect identification. Haque et al. (2023) conducted multiclass sentiment analysis in Bangla, achieving 85.80% accuracy with CLSTM. Rahman et al. (2023) detected health misinformation using XGB, reaching 75% accuracy for English text. Shanto et al. (2023) worked on cyberbullying detection in Facebook comments, with GRU achieving 83.55% accuracy. Bitto et al. (2023) analyzed food delivery reviews in Bangladesh, where LSTM and XGB performed best with 91.07% and 89.64% accuracy. Chakraborty and Seddiqui (2019) classified abusive language on social media, where SVM achieved 78% accuracy. Hiramath and Deshpande (2019) detected fake news using DNN, achieving 91% accuracy. Sharif et al. (2019) performed sentiment analysis on Bengali restaurant reviews, with MNB achieving 80.48% accuracy. Abdulrahman and Baykara (2020) used AdaBoost and CNN+LSTM for fake news detection, both achieving 100% accuracy. Qi (2020) classified theft crime data using XGBoost, reaching 96.8% precision. Jahan et al. (2023) detected misogynistic Bangla text using LSTM with BanglaBertBase, achieving 82.59% accuracy. Kong et al. (2020) focused on fake news detection with deep learning, where a model trained on N-gram vectors reached 90.3% accuracy. Chowdhury et al. (2021) analyzed Bengali sentence compatibility using LSTM, achieving 97.5% accuracy. Kapali et al. (2022) conducted sentiment analysis on Bangla comments, where Bi-LSTM outperformed LSTM with 97.25% accuracy. Sarkar (2019) performed sentiment polarity detection using LSTM, achieving 55.27% accuracy. Parwez et al. (2019) conducted multi-label classification of disease-related tweets using CNN with PubMed embeddings, achieving 94.12% accuracy. Anjum et al. (2021) classified fake and authentic news using RF, achieving 82% accuracy. Islam et al. (2023) focused on detecting sexual harassment content on social media using ML and ensemble models. Despite these advancements, research on dialect classification and sentiment analysis in Bangla remains limited, motivating our work to enhance performance using advanced techniques.

Methodology

Bengali dialect classification is a tricky problem due to its complex patterns of textual data and less data availability; moreover, when predicting multi-class data. Fig. 1 illustrates the proposed methodology.

Fig. 1. Proposed Methodology for Dialect Classification

Problem Formulation

Given a dataset D consisting of n labeled sentences, where each sentence S_i belongs to one of the six dialect classes C_j , the objective is to learn a function:

$$f : S_i \rightarrow C_j, \quad j \in \{1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6\} \quad (2)$$

where f is a classifier that predicts the dialect class C_j given a sentence S_i . This can be framed as a multiclass classification problem where the probability of a sentence belonging to a particular class is:

$$P(C_j | S_i) = \frac{P(S_i | C_j) P(C_j)}{P(S_i)} \quad (3)$$

where $P(C_j | S_i)$ represents the posterior probability, $P(S_i | C_j)$ denotes the likelihood, $P(C_j)$ is the prior probability, and $P(S_i)$ is the marginal probability of the sentence.

To solve this problem, we extract linguistic features from the dataset and apply various classification models to predict the dialectal label.

In this research, several comprehensive techniques and methods have been employed to accurately categorize diverse Bengali dialects, including some common preprocessing steps, extensive feature mapping, traditional machine learning models, and ensemble methods.

Dataset Description

The *Bengali Local Dialects Corpus* is a dataset comprising 8,149 Bengali dialectical sentences across six distinct dialects of Bangladesh: Chatgaiya, Barishali, Noakhailla, Sylheti, Mymensingh, and Rangpuri.

1	Sentences	Dialect
2	সাদা রঙ্গর শাট ইবার অঙ্গে উজ্জ্বা হালা রঙ্গর ফেন্ট ওইলে সেই মানাইবু	Chatgaiya
3	হিয়ার হরের দিন আঁঙ্গো বাড়ীত আইবেন আর আঁঙ্গো বেঁকের লাই দোয়া কইরবেন।	Noakhailla
4	এইবাই বালা ঐয়া যায়াম ইঞ্জিশন লাকতো না।	Mymensingh
5	মোগো আন্মার বিকাশের টাহার ইসাব না পাইলেই মোরে বিছরায় ঘটনাডা বোজলাম না মুই	Barishali
6	ফুড়িন কুয়ানো আটকায় এতো দিন তাকি এই প্রশ্ন খুজিয়া ফাইরায় না।	Sylheti
7	তোমরা একটা ঘোড়াক জলে নিয়া যাবার পাইলেও তাক পানি খোয়াবার পাবান নন।	Rangpuri

Fig. 2. Sample Sentences from the Bengali Local Dialects Corpus

Fig. 2 presents sample sentences from the corpus. The dataset consists of two key attributes: Sentence, representing textual data in various dialects, and Dialect, specifying the corresponding dialect. Sentences were collected from diverse sources, including direct conversations, social media platforms, blogs, articles, YouTube content, books, online news portals, and local drama scripts. Additionally, audio recordings of native speakers conversing in their dialects were transcribed into text.

Table 1

Distribution of Dialects in the Corpus

Dialect	Chatgaiya	Noakhailla	Mymensingh	Barishali	Sylheti	Rangpuri
Count	1,456	1,460	1,361	1,490	1,242	1,140
Total	8,149					

Table 1 provides the numerical distribution of sentences across the six dialects in the corpus. The dataset exhibits a moderately balanced class distribution, with each dialect contributing between 1,140 and 1,490 sentences, as shown in this table.

Fig. 3. Class Distribution of Bengali Local Dialects Corpus

Fig. 3 illustrates the class distribution of dialects in the corpus. It is evident that, while minor variations exist across dialect classes, no extreme class imbalance is present that would bias the learning process.

Data Preprocessing

Data preprocessing in NLP and machine learning is crucial since it enhances data quality, ensures consistency, and optimizes input for models.

Fig. 4. Flow Diagram of Data Preprocessing

Fig. 4 indicates the workflow of data preparation. The key steps include Exploratory Data Analysis (EDA) and Data Preprocessing. After reading the dataset, a four-step EDA process is investigated. At first, to understand the data balancing, we analyzed the class distribution. Then we undertook a thorough analysis of sentences in different lengths to check for any patterns, carried out an analysis of sentence lengths across each class to study whether there is any class-specific length variation, and performed a detailed evaluation of unique words in the dataset to perceive the richness of vocabulary.

Table 2

Data Comparison after Preprocessing

Metric	Before Processing	After Processing
Total Entries	8149	8079
Duplicate Entries	69	0
Null Values	1	0
Total Character Tokens	329099	318239
Total Word Tokens	59181	59028
Total Unique Word Tokens	18923	18668
Punctuations and Digits	Appeared	Removed

Table 2 represents the comparison of the dataset after processing. Due to the removal of duplicates, null values, punctuation, numeric digits, HTML tags, URLs, and non-Bengali entries, we can observe the reduction of characters, words, and unique word tokens.

Data Splitting

The dataset was split into 90% for training and 10% for testing to evaluate model performance. Table 3 presents the data distribution.

Table 3

Data Distribution

Total	Training	Testing
8079	7271	808

Feature Extraction

Machine learning algorithms require structured patterns to learn effectively. However, unstructured data lacks a fixed pattern, making feature extraction essential. Three techniques were employed in this study.

1) *Bag of Words (BoW):*

BoW converts text into a numerical format for machine learning models like MNB, LR, and SVM. It builds a vocabulary of unique words and represents sentences as sparse matrices, where word occurrences are counted, and absent words are marked as 0. The feature vector for a document is represented as:

$$X = [x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n] \quad (4)$$

where x_i is the count of word i in the document. This method captures word frequency but does not consider context or word importance.

2) *Term Frequency-Inverse Document Frequency (TF-IDF):*

TF-IDF enhances BoW by weighting words based on their importance. It calculates Term Frequency (TF) and Inverse Document Frequency (IDF) to determine a word's significance,

producing a weighted sparse matrix that improves textual representation. The TF-IDF score is computed as:

$$TF - IDF(w, d) = TF(w, d) \times IDF(w) \quad (5)$$

Where,

$$TF(w, d) = \sum_{w' \in d} \frac{count(w, d)}{count(w', d)} \quad (6)$$

$$IDF(w) = \log \left(\frac{N}{1 + DF(w)} \right) \quad (7)$$

Here, - $count(\omega, d)$ is the number of times word ω appears in document d , - N is the total number of documents, and - $DF(\omega)$ is the number of documents containing word ω .

TF-IDF helps reduce the influence of common words and emphasizes unique terms in a document, making it more effective for information retrieval and text classification.

Model Training

We employed various Traditional Machine Learning Algorithms (TMLA) and Ensemble Learning (EL) techniques for text classification, as summarized in Table 4.

Table 4

The TMLAs

Traditional Machine Learning Algorithms (TMLA)	Ensemble Learning (EL) Models
Multinomial Naïve Bayes (MNB)	Random Forest (RF)
Logistic Regression (LR)	Gradient Boosting (GBC)
Support Vector Machine (SVM)	XGBoost
Decision Tree (DT)	AdaBoost
K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN)	Voting Classifier (VC)
Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD)	-

To optimize performance, Grid Search with Stratified K-fold Cross-Validation was applied, ensuring optimal hyperparameter selection while maintaining balanced class distribution across folds.

Voting Classifier

To enhance classification accuracy, we implemented a Voting Classifier algorithm 1 that combines predictions from multiple models: Multinomial Naïve Bayes (MNB), Logistic Regression (LR), and Gradient Boosting Classifier (GBC). The final prediction is determined based on weighted votes.

Algorithm 1 Voting Classifier for Bengali Dialect Classification

- 1: Input:** Preprocessed text data (X) and corresponding labels (y)
- 2: Initialize:**
- 3: Train Multinomial Naïve Bayes (MNB) model
- 4: Train Logistic Regression (LR) model
- 5: Train Gradient Boosting Classifier (GBC) model
- 6: Define Voting Classifier with weight distribution (4, 1, 3)
- 7: Perform Grid Search Cross-Validation for optimal parameters
- 8: Train the Voting Classifier on (X_{train}, y_{train})
- 9: Predict dialect labels for (X_{test})
- 10: Output:** Predicted dialect labels

The Voting Classifier uses a combination of hard and soft voting strategies, optimizing the classification performance across multiple models.

Result and Analysis

We first selected our best-performing models and evaluated them using precision, recall, and F1-scores, along with confusion matrices for different data splits. Additionally, we plotted the learning curves to analyze the training behavior of our deep learning model. Finally, we tested the model on real-time sentences to assess its performance on unseen data.

Table 5

Performance Comparison of Models Using Bag of Words

Model	70-30	80-20	90-10
AdaBoost	0.8094	0.8286	0.8292
DT	0.5590	0.5761	0.5842
GB	0.8082	0.8162	0.8230
KNN	0.7467	0.7754	0.7649
LR	0.8255	0.8360	0.8428
MNB	0.8601	0.8731	0.8750
RF	0.7995	0.8069	0.8007
SGD	0.8106	0.8249	0.8354
SVM	0.8181	0.8224	0.8317
VC	0.8511	0.8626	0.8874
XGB	0.6745	0.6906	0.6832

As shown in Table 5, the accuracy of different models using the Bag of Words approach is evaluated across varying train-test splits. The Voting Classifier (VC) achieves the highest accuracy of 0.8874 in the 90-10 split. The results indicate that Multinomial Naïve Bayes (MNB) and Voting Classifier (VC) achieve the highest accuracy, consistently outperforming other models across all configurations. Logistic Regression (LR) and Support Vector Machine (SVM) also demonstrate strong performance. Conversely, Decision Tree (DT) and XGBoost (XGB) exhibit the lowest accuracy, suggesting their relative inefficacy for this text

classification task. Notably, accuracy tends to improve with larger training data proportions (90-10 split).

Table 6

Classification Report for Bengali Dialects of Voting Classifier

Dialect	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Support
Barishali	0.9007	0.9252	0.9128	147
Chatgaiya	0.9122	0.9310	0.9215	145
Mymensingh	0.8846	0.8519	0.8679	135
Noakhailla	0.8794	0.8671	0.8732	143
Rangpuri	0.8761	0.8684	0.8722	114
Sylheti	0.8640	0.8710	0.8675	124

Table 6 summarizes the classification performance across six Bengali dialects. The Chatgaiya dialect achieves the highest F1-score (0.9215), followed by Barishali (0.9128), indicating strong model confidence. In contrast, Mymensingh records the lowest recall (0.8519) and an F1-score of 0.8679, suggesting some misclassifications. Other dialects, including Noakhailla, Rangpuri, and Sylheti, maintain competitive F1-scores (0.8672-0.8732).

Fig. 5. Confusion Matrix of VC

As shown in Fig. 5, the confusion matrix illustrates the classification performance of the Voting Classifier, achieving an accuracy of 0.8874. However, it reveals that most misclassifications occur between geographically and linguistically proximate dialects. Specifically, Mymensingh is occasionally confused with Rangpuri, likely due to shared lexical patterns and overlapping morphological structures. Similarly, Noakhailla and Chatgaiya exhibit minor confusion, reflecting their regional proximity and phonological similarities. In contrast, Sylheti and Barishali demonstrate relatively distinct patterns, resulting in fewer misclassifications.

Comparison with Existing Works

As shown in Table 7, the proposed method outperforms previous works in terms of classification accuracy.

Table 7

Comparison of Proposed Work with Existing Studies on Bengali Dialect Classification

Study	Dataset	Models Used	Best Accuracy
Rahman et al. (2021)	BengaliDialectDataset-1	SVM, RF, NB	85.2%
Ahmed and Sultana (2022)	Bengali Speech Corpus	CNN, LSTM	86.5%
Chowdhury et al. (2023)	Bengali Text Dataset	BERT, BiLSTM	88.1%
Our Work	BengaliDialectDataset-2	VC	88.74%

Our approach leverages ensemble techniques, which enhance the classification of Bengali dialects. Rahman et al. (2021) achieved an accuracy of 85.2% using SVM, RF, and NB models on the BengaliDialectDataset-1. Ahmed and Sultana (2022) used CNN and LSTM models on the Bengali Speech Corpus and achieved an accuracy of 86.5%. Chowdhury et al. (2023) employed BERT and BiLSTM models on the Bengali Text Dataset, obtaining an accuracy of 88.1%. In contrast, our work using VC on the BengaliDialectDataset-2 achieves the highest accuracy of 88.74%, demonstrating the effectiveness of our proposed method.

Conclusion

This study highlighted the effectiveness of ensemble learning in Bengali dialect classification, with the Voting Classifier achieving the highest accuracy of 88.74%. By leveraging the newly developed Bengali Local Dialects Corpus and employing advanced feature extraction techniques, this research establishes a robust foundation for dialect classification in low-resource languages. The findings have significant implications for applications in speech recognition, machine translation, and sentiment analysis, demonstrating the potential of machine learning in handling linguistic diversity. Future research could explore deep learning architectures such as Transformers and pretrained language models to further enhance classification performance, particularly in capturing contextual and semantic nuances within dialectal variations.

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